

AI Ethics Principles and Challenges: Industrial and Legislation Insights

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

RESEARCH TITLE

AI Ethics Principles and Challenges: Industrial Insights

RESEARCHERS INFORMATION

The contact details of each researcher are provided at the end of the page.

DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are considered important across a vast array of industries including health, manufacturing, banking and retail. However, the promises of AI systems like improving productivity, reducing costs, and safety has now been considered with worries, that these complex systems might bring more ethical harm than economical good.

The aim of this survey study is to get the understanding of the key principles of AI ethics and the challenges that could negatively impact the AI ethics principles.

If you are a practitioner who has experience and domain knowledge in AI systems development or lawmaker having expertise in AI technologies and policies, then you are invited to participate in this research survey. Your response would be highly acknowledged.

SURVEY PROCEDURE

You will be requested to complete the survey questionnaire, which will take approximately 15-20 minutes. You will be asked a number of questions related to AI ethics principles, challenges and the impact of the challenges on AI ethics principles.

DATA REPOSITORY

The collected data will be stored and keep on password protected account. The data will be analysed and the results will only be used for research purposes and publications. All the results to the survey participants will only be available upon the request.

PRIVACY OF COLLECTED DATA

Information gathered from this questionnaire will strictly be confidential. Entire information will be used for research purposes only and will not be shared with third party under any circumstances.

For more details, browse the following links for "Research Notification" and "Privacy Notice" details:

<https://tinyurl.com/67nek3ce> (Research Notification)

<https://tinyurl.com/4hbcku8n> (Privacy Notice)

CONTACTS DETAIL

In case of any query regarding the survey, you can contact Arif Ali Khan (arif.khan@oulu.fi), Muhammad Waseem (m.waseem@whu.edu.cn), Peng Liang (liangp@whu.edu.cn), and Pekka Abrahamsson (pekka.abrahamsson@jyu.fi).

You may also contact at (+358)-403291085.

*Required

Untitled section

1. I agree to participate in this research survey by completing the questionnaire. I understand that only the researcher will have access to the collected data. I understand that the results of this study will be available from the researchers upon the request. I also understand that the researchers will not disclose my identity in any research publication that results from this survey. I agree to participate in this research survey under the terms and conditions provided to me.

Tick all that apply.

- Yes
 No

Section- A (Respondent Information)

2. Full Name (Optional)

3. Email Address *

4. Current position in industry / Law forum *

5. In which country you are presently working? *

6. What kind of software projects your company develops/ What kind of technology cases your law firm deals with? *

7. What is the size of your organization (number of employees)? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1-9
- 10-49
- 50-249
- 250-499
- >500
- Other: _____

8. Working experience (Years) as software practitioner/ technology lawmaker. *

Mark only one oval.

- 0-2 Years
- 3-5 Years
- 6-10 Years
- >10 Years

9. Have you ever been participated in Artificial Intelligence (AI) project as software practitioner/ technology lawmaker? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure
- Other: _____

10. Working experience (Years) in AI related projects as practitioner/ technology lawmaker? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0-2 Years
- 3-5 Years
- 6-10 Years
- >10 Years

11. Does your organisation consider ethics in AI based software systems/ develop policies for AI ethics? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure
- Other: _____

**Section-
B1 (AI
Ethics
Principles)**

The aim of this section is to specify the principles that one should consider for deploying ethics in AI-based software systems. We extracted various AI ethics principles from the literature using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach.

12. Please rank the significance of each principle according to your own understanding and experience. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Extremely Agree	Moderately Agree	Slightly Agree	Neutral	Slightly Disagree	Moderately Disagree
Transparency: AI system decision making process should be transparent.	<input type="radio"/>					
Privacy: Assure user and data privacy throughout the system lifecycle.	<input type="radio"/>					
Accountability: Safeguard justice by assigning responsibility and prevent harm.	<input type="radio"/>					
Fairness: AI system should not make discrimination between individuals or groups.	<input type="radio"/>					
Autonomy: Design AI system for human autonomy.	<input type="radio"/>					
Explainability: Understand how the AI system makes the autonomous decision.	<input type="radio"/>					
Justice: AI system should promote justice and remove discrimination.	<input type="radio"/>					
Non-	<input type="radio"/>					

maleficence:
Avoid misuse of AI systems.

Human dignity:
AI system should not compromise on human values intrinsic to humanity.

Beneficence: AI systems promotes well-being.

Responsibility:
Designing, developing, and deploying AI systems with good intention to empower humanity.

Safety: AI systems should not bring personal and societal harm.

Data security: AI systems should ensure the security of data.

Sustainability:
AI system should be ethically sustainable.

Freedom: AI system should respect human freedom and autonomy.

Solidarity: Share the AI system productivity, gains, and losses.

Prosperity:
Share the

**prosperity brings
by AI systems.**

Effectiveness:
**AI system should
be socially and
technically
effective.**

Accuracy: AI
**systems produce
reliable and
accurate
outcomes.**

Predictability:
**The long-term
implications of the
AI system should
be predictable.**

Interpretability:
**Decision making
process of the AI
system should be
interpretable.**

13. Add new principles based on your experience apart from the above listed ones.

Section-B2
(AI Ethics
Challenges)

The aim of this section is to specify the challenging factors that could negatively impact ethics in AI environment. We extracted various challenging factors from the literature using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach.

14. Please rank the significance of each factor according to your own understanding and experience. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Extremely Agree	Moderately Agree	Slightly Agree	Neutral	Slightly Disagree	Moderately Disagree
<p>Lack of ethical knowledge: Limited knowledge regarding ethical codes and standards.</p>	<input type="radio"/>					
<p>Vague principles: Ethical principles are unclear in their definition.</p>	<input type="radio"/>					
<p>Highly general principles: Principles are general and broad in concept to specifically map in the AI domain.</p>	<input type="radio"/>					
<p>Conflict in practice: Organizations, committees, and groups developing the AI ethics guidelines and principles have opinion conflicts regarding the real-world implementation of AI ethics.</p>	<input type="radio"/>					
<p>Interpret principles differently: AI ethics principles are widely considered ambiguous by</p>	<input type="radio"/>					

the majority of organizations.

Lack of technical understanding: AI ethics policymakers and regulatory bodies might not have a good technical understanding of AI technologies.

Extra constraints: Additional constraints to develop an AI system in ethical fashion is even harder task.

Lacking monitoring bodies: Lack of regulatory oversight to monitor ethics in AI systems.

No legal frameworks: Unavailability of AI ethics assessment frameworks.

Business interest: Prefer business gains over ethical considerations.

Pluralism of ethical methods: Various ethical methods are available and its hard to decide

and select the suitable one.

Cases of ethical dilemmas:

Conflict between selecting alternative ethical requirements.

Machine distortion:

Information misinterpretation and falsification by AI system.

Lack of guidance and adoption: Lack of standard and general AI ethics guidelines and practices.

Lack of cross-cultural cooperation: Lack of international cooperation on AI ethics governance and standarization.

15. Add new challenging factor based on your experience apart from the above listed ones.

**Section-C
(Rate the
Severity
(Impact) of
Challenging
Factors
Related to
the
Principles)**

The aim of this section is to specify the impact of frequently cited challenging factors with respect to the frequently reported principles. We provided the severity measurement scale to evaluate the impact of challenging factors on the AI ethics principles. Please rank the severity level for each principle based on your own understanding and experience.

Note that in this section we only considered the SLR study challenging factors and principles having frequency of occurrence greater than one. Finally, we shortlisted seven challenging factors and six principles.

The details description of each selected challenging factor and principle are provided at the following links:

Principles: <https://tinyurl.com/ua8d9e8a>

Challenging factors: <https://tinyurl.com/57ze8jwd>

16. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the **Transparency** principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

17. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the **Privacy** principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

18. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the **Accountability** principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

19. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the ***Fairness*** principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

20. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the **Autonomy** principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

21. How do you rate the severity of each challenging factor with respect to the *Explainability* principle? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic (extremely sever)
Lack of ethical Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Vague principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Highly general principles	<input type="radio"/>				
Conflict in practice	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpret principles differently	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of technical understanding	<input type="radio"/>				
Extra constraints	<input type="radio"/>				

Thank you very much for your time to take this survey. Your response is contributing to our research.

Arif Ali Khan
 (arif.khan@oulu.fi),
 Muhammad Waseem
 (m.waseem@whu.edu.cn),
 Peng Liang
 (liangp@whu.edu.cn),
 Pekka Abrahamsson
 (pekka.abrahamsson@jyu.fi),

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